

Synthesis and study of new mesogenic homologous series : 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)naphthyl azo benzenes

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Abstract : Mesogenic homologous series : 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl azo benzenes has been synthesized and their mesogenic properties are studied. All the derivatives exhibit enantiotropic nematic mesophase from very first member of the series. Smectic mesophase does not occur by any derivative of the series. Well known odd-even effect is observed in the nematic isotropic transition curve with alternation of transition temperatures. The behaviour of the series and its average thermal stabilities are compared with structurally related series.

Keywords : Azo mesogens, smectic, nematic.

Homologous series with -COO- and -N=N- central bridges, (azo ester homologous series) has been synthesized and its liquid crystalline properties compared with other structurally similar series¹. A vast number of mesogenic naphthalene derivatives are reported in the literature², as naphthalene derivatives exhibit rich mesomorphism if properly designed.

Experimental

p-Hydroxy-naphthyl azo benzene was prepared from aniline and α -naphthol by routine diazotisation process. *p*-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyl chlorides were reacted with azo dye to form azo esters³. Azo esters were purified in alcohol. Analytical data confirms the structure. Analysis of nitrogen (%), Found (Calcd.) of *n*-alkyl group : methyl 7.40 (7.56), ethyl 7.00 (7.29), propyl 6.99 (7.03), butyl 6.60 (6.79), pentyl 6.47 (6.57), hexyl 6.01 (6.36), heptyl 5.90 (6.16), octyl 5.80 (5.98), decyl 5.54 (5.64), dodecyl 5.14 (5.34) and tetradecyl 5.00 (5.07). IR and NMR spectral data : butyl (IR) 1419, 2871, 2919 cm^{-1} , alkyl group; 1068, 1733 cm^{-1} , -COO- group; 1254 cm^{-1} , C-O (ether) group; 1171 cm^{-1} , C-N str. due to -N=N- group; 853 cm^{-1} , *para*- substituted benzene : dodecyl (IR) 1455, 2852, 2925 cm^{-1} , alkyl group; 1019, 1698, 1733 cm^{-1} , -COO- group; 1168 cm^{-1} , C-N str. due to -N=N- group; 1574 cm^{-1} , -N=N- bending; 850 cm^{-1} , *para*-substituted benzene : propyl (NMR) 1.015 (3H, t, -CH₃), 1.052 (2H, m,

-CH₂), 3.98 (2H, t, -OCH₂), 6.9-8.06 (15H, m, Ar-H); pentyl (NMR) 0.94 (3H, t, -CH₃), 1.25 (6H, m, -CH₂), 4.02 (2H, t, -OCH₂), 6.91-8.07 (15H, m, Ar-H). Transition temperatures are recorded in Table 1. The transition temperatures of the members of the title homologous series were observed through hot stage polarizing microscope.

Results and discussion

4-Hydroxy-naphthyl azo benzene is a non-mesogenic

Table 1. Transition temperatures for 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl azo benzenes

No. of carbon atoms in <i>n</i> -alkyl chain	Transition temp. (°C)	
	Nematic	Isotropic
1	75.0	116.0
2	87.0	140.0
3	125.0	142.0
4	115.0	151.0
5	117.0	144.0
6	93.0	150.0
7	96.0	146.0
8	88.0	150.0
10	113.0	151.0
12	105.0	140.0
14	86.0	115.0

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substance but linking of phenyl ring bridged through -COO- and left *n*-alkoxy terminal increases the length of the molecules which enhances intermolecular attractions and polarizability. Homologous series 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-naphthyl azo benzenes is purely nematogenic with middle ordered melting type. All the members exhibit mesomorphism from first to the last member of homologous series. All the derivatives are enantiotropic nematic and smoothly transform into isotropic liquid at definite temperature. Smectic mesophase does not appear in case of any homologue of the series and hence polymesomorphism is not displayed by any homologue of the series. The plot of transition temperatures versus the number of carbon atoms in *n*-

alkyl chain (Fig. 1); follows a zig-zag path of rising and falling tendency as usual for solid-mesomorphic transition curve. Well known odd-even effect is observed in the nematic-isotropic transition curve with alternation of transition temperatures. The mesomorphic-isotropic transition temperatures are between 115 °C and 151 °C with mesomorphic range varying from 17 °C to a maximum of 62 °C at the third homologue and eighth homologue of the series, respectively. The title homologous series is considered as middle ordered melting type with short range of liquid crystallinity. Liquid crystals of moderate chain lengths yield only nematogenic homologues; is well supported by present investigation.

The present homologous series (1) is compared with

Fig. 1. 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl azo benzenes.

Series (1). 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl azo benzenes.

Series (2). 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-phenyl azo benzenes.

structurally similar other homologous series (2⁴); for their molecular characteristics and thermal stabilities which are : nematic-isotropic 140.45 for series (1) are (C₁-C₄), and 145.0 for series (2) are (C₁-C₈), nematic phase starts at C₁.

Series (1) and (2) differ only in one phenyl ring at the middle part of the molecule without terminal end group. Hence, the variation in mesomorphic properties and degree of mesomorphism are varied due to additional phenyl ring at middle part for series (1) and (2).

Gray³ has explained that increase in the breadth of the molecules reduces both nematic and smectic mesophase stability. It seems that the naphthyl ring does not increase only the breadth but also increases the coplanarity in the molecular system due to steric interaction. Both these factors could eliminate the smectogenic behaviour in case of series (1). Nematic-isotropic thermal stability of series (1) is lower than series (2). This is because of broadening of molecule as concluded by Gray for series (1). The molecules of all homologues of the series are capable of resisting the strong thermal vibrations at high temperatures and yield anisotropic liquids. The molecules set themselves parallel to each other in a floating condition, giving rise

to a threaded texture of nematic mesophase enantiotropically.

Thus nematic group efficiency order is derived from above discussion for lateral position.

-H > additional phenyl ring
(i.e. naphthyl derivative)

Conclusion :

Present investigation supports Gray's view, that broadening of a molecule reduces thermal stability for nematic and smectic mesophases.

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